

Synthesis of some Arylidenehydrazinothiazoles and their Antimicrobial Activities

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Eight new arylidenehydrazinothiazole derivatives have been prepared and their structures elucidated by elemental analysis, uv, ir, nmr, and mass spectral data. The compounds have been tested for their antibacterial activities against *S. faecalis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*.

THIOSEMICARBAZONES and thiazolyhydrazones are known to possess various pharmacological activities. It has been shown that alkyl, aryl and heteroaryl substituted thiazolyhydrazones have such activities¹.

The present paper reports the synthesis of eight new compounds having 2-arylidenehydrazino-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole structure and determine their antimicrobial activities on various microorganisms.

1. $R_1 = H, R_2 = H, R_3 = H$
2. $R_1 = OH, R_2 = H, R_3 = H$
3. $R_1 = H, R_2 = OH, R_3 = H$
4. $R_1 = H, R_2 = H, R_3 = OH$
5. $R_1 = H, R_2 = OH, R_3 = OH$
6. $R_1 = H, R_2 = OH, R_3 = OOH$
7. $R_1 = H, R_2 = OOH, R_3 = OH$
8. $R_1 = H, R_2 = OOH, R_3 = OOH$

Experimental

Benzaldehyde, 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde, 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, 3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde, 3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 2-bromopropionic acid, 5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone and thiosemicarbazide (Merck and Aldrich) were used. 3-Methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone was prepared by methylation of 5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone with dimethyl sulphate².

Melting points of the compounds were determined using a Thomas Hoover capillary melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Uv spectra (MeOH) of the compounds were run on a Hitachi 220S spectrophotometer at $5 \times 10^{-5} M$

concentration, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 457 grating spectrophotometer, nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Bruker 200 MHz spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard and mass spectra on a Bruker instrument. Elemental analyses of the compounds were performed at Mainz (West Germany).

2-Arylidenehydrazino-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazoles: A mixture of equimolar amounts of aldehyde thiosemicarbazone and 3-methyl-5-chloro-6-(2-bromopropionyl)-2-benzoxazolinone was refluxed in methanol for 2 h. The solution was then evaporated to dryness under diminished pressure. The resulting precipitate was crystallised from appropriate solvent.

2-Benzylidenehydrazino-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole (1): It was obtained as yellow crystals (methanol; 79.14%), m.p. 266° (Found: C, 57.00; H, 3.68; N, 13.91. $C_{15}H_{15}ClN_4O_2S$ calcd. for: C, 57.21; H, 3.79; N, 14.05%); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 338 (4.13), 242 (4.24) and 221 nm (4.32); ν_{max} 3030 (CH, s, Ar), 1770 (C=O, s, lactam), 1550, 1470 (C=C, C=N), 735 and 690 cm^{-1} (CH, b, monosubstituted-benzene); δ 2.14 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.37 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 5.74 (1H, s, NH-N), 7.36-7.66 (7H, m, ArH) and 8.00 (1H, s, N=CH); m/z 400, 398 (M^+), 297, 296, 295, (% 100), 261, 260, 259, 253, 218, 77 and 59.

2-(2-Hydroxybenzylidenehydrazino)-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole (2): It was obtained as yellow crystals (methanol; 85.15%), m.p. 294° (Found: C, 55.13; H, 3.58; N, 13.31. $C_{15}H_{15}ClN_4O_3S$ calcd. for: C, 55.01; H, 3.64; N, 13.51%); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 345 (3.97), 293 (3.83), 240 (4.10) and 221 nm (4.29); ν_{max} 3150 (OH, s), 3040 (CH, s, Ar), 1765 (C=O, s, lactam), 1550, 1470 (C=C, C=N, s), 740 cm^{-1} (CH, b, monosubstituted-benzene); δ 2.15 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.35 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 5.74 (1H, s, NH-N), 6.79-7.54 (6H, m, ArH), 7.90 (1H, s, N=CH), 9.58 (1H, s, OH); m/z 416, 414 (M^+) (% 100), 297, 296, 295, 260, 259, 258, 253, 218, 121, 77, 59 and 57.

2-(3-Hydroxybenzylidenehydrazino)-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole (3): It was obtained as yellow crystals (isopropanol; 82.14%), m.p. 210° (Found: C, 54.78; H, 3.43; N, 13.62. $C_{21}H_{16}ClN_4O_4S$ calcd. for: C, 55.01; H, 3.64; N, 13.51%); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 343 (3.89), 292 (3.81), 239 (4.07) and 220 nm (4.40); ν_{max} 3 200 (OH, s), 3 040 (CH, s, Ar), 1 775 (C=O, s, lactam), 1 555, 1 465 (C=C, C=N, s) and 830 cm^{-1} (CH, b, 1,3-disubstituted-benzene); δ 2.14 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.36 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 5.76 (1H, s, NH), 6.80–7.55 (6H, m, ArH), 7.89 (1H, s, N=CH) and 9.59 (1H, s, OH); m/z 416, 414 (M^+), 297, 296, 295 (% 100), 260, 259, 253, 218, 120, 93, 77, 65 and 59.

2-(4-Hydroxybenzylidenehydrazino)-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole (4): It was obtained as white crystals (methanol; 89.83%), m.p. 254° (Found: C, 55.14; H, 3.64; N, 13.39. $C_{21}H_{16}ClN_4O_4S$ calcd. for: C, 55.01; H, 3.64; N, 13.51%); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 344 (3.92), 294 (3.83), 241 (4.12) and 219 nm (4.27); ν_{max} 3 400–3 200 (OH, s), 3 045 (CH, s, Ar), 1 740 (C=O, s, lactam), 1 575, 1 480 (C=C, C=N, s) and 830 cm^{-1} (CH, b, 1,4-disubstituted-benzene); δ 2.12 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.37 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 5.76 (1H, s, NH), 6.83–7.53 (6H, m, ArH), 7.89 (1H, s, N=CH) and 9.82 (1H, s, OH); m/z 416, 414 (M^+), 297, 296, 295, 260, 259, 253, 218, 156, 97, 71 and 55 (% 100).

2-(3,4-Dihydroxybenzylidenehydrazino)-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole (5): It was obtained as white crystals (methanol; 72.77%), m.p. 251° (Found: C, 52.80; H, 3.60; N, 12.88. $C_{21}H_{16}ClN_4O_4S$ calcd. for: C, 52.97; H, 3.51; N, 13.00%); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 843 (4.48), 293 (4.21), 241 (4.11) and 220 nm (4.45); ν_{max} 3 450–3 100 (OH, s), 3 030 (CH, s, Ar), 1 735 (C=O, s, lactam), 1 580, 1 485 (C=C, C=N, s) and 780 cm^{-1} (CH, b, 1,2,4-trisubstituted-benzene); δ 2.12 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.37 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 5.76 (1H, s, NH), 6.74–7.54 (5H, m, ArH), 7.81 (1H, s, N=CH) and 9.21–9.32 (2H, d, 2 \times OH); m/z 432, 430 (M^+), 398, 297, 296, 295 (% 100), 260, 259, 253, 218, 77 and 57.

2-(3-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzylidenehydrazino)-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole (6): It was obtained as white crystals (isopropanol; 90.13%), m.p. 227° (Found: C, 53.77; H, 3.91; N, 12.42. $C_{20}H_{17}ClN_4O_4S$ calcd. for: C, 53.99; H, 3.85; N, 12.59%); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 345 (4.36), 295 (4.16), 240 (4.07) and 220 nm (4.43); ν_{max} 3 400 (OH, s), 3 040 (CH, s, Ar), 1 755 (C=O, s, lactam), 1 550, 1 450 (C=C, C=N, s), 1 240 (C-O, s) and 780 cm^{-1} (C-H, b, 1,2,4-trisubstituted-benzene); δ 2.12 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.36 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.76 (1H, s, NH), 6.79–7.55 (5H, m, ArH), 8.29 (1H, s, N=CH), and 9.62 (1H, s, OH); m/z 446, 444 (M^+), 429, 297, 296, 295 (% 100), 260, 259, 258, 253, 218, 151, 150, 122, 108, 106 and 65.

2-(3-Methoxy-4-hydroxybenzylidenehydrazino)-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole (7): It was obtained as white crystals (methanol; 71.73%, m.p. 202°) (Found: C, 53.61; H, 4.05; N, 12.70. $C_{20}H_{17}ClN_4O_4S$ calcd. for: C,

53.99; H, 3.85; N, 12.59%); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 346 (4.32), 293 (4.11), 242 (4.03) and 219 nm (4.40); ν_{max} 3 400 (OH, s), 3 040 (CH, s, Ar), 1 750 (C=O, s, lactam), 1 575, 1 485 (C=C, C=N, s), 1 255 (C-O, s) and 780 cm^{-1} (CH, b, 1,2,4-trisubstituted-benzene); δ 2.12 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.35 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.75 (1H, s, NH), 6.83–7.54 (5H, m, ArH), 7.88 (1H, s, N=CH) and 9.44 (1H, s, OH); m/z 446, 444 (M^+), 297, 296, 295 (% 100), 260, 259, 253, 218, 150, 65 and 59.

2-(3,4-Dimethoxybenzylidenehydrazino)-4-(3-methyl-5-chloro-3-benzoxazolinone-6-yl)-5-methylthiazole (8): It was obtained as yellow crystals (isopropanol; 74.14%, m.p. 230°) (Found: C, 55.01; H, 4.00; N, 12.33. $C_{21}H_{16}ClN_4O_4S$ calcd. for: C, 54.96; H, 4.17; N, 12.21%); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 343 (4.28), 292 (4.09), 240 (4.14) and 220 nm (4.36); ν_{max} 3 040 (CH, s, Ar), 1 755 (C=O, s, lactam), 1 580, 1 480 (C=C, C=N, s), 1 250 (C-O, s) and 780 cm^{-1} (CH, b, 1,2,4-trisubstituted-benzene); δ 2.13 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.35 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 3.79 (6H, s, OCH_3), 5.55 (1H, s, NH), 6.98–7.55 (5H, m, ArH) and 7.91 (1H, s, N=CH); m/z 460, 458 (M^+), 297, 296, 295 (% 100), 260, 259, 258, 253, 218, 150, 107, 92, 79, 77, 66 and 59.

Microbiology: Antibacterial properties of the compounds were screened against four microorganisms, viz. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus faecalis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* by tube dilution method⁸. M.I.C. of all the compounds (1–8) were found to be > 400 $\mu g\ ml^{-1}$ against all the four microorganisms.

Results and Discussion

In order to synthesise the compounds, corresponding thiosemicarbazone and 3-methyl-5-chloro-6-(2-bromopropionyl)-2-benzoxazolinone were heated in methanol.

3-Methyl-5-chloro-6-(2-bromopropionyl)-2-benzoxazolinone was prepared by heating 3-methyl-5-chloro-2-benzoxazolinone and 2-bromopropionic acid in polyphosphoric acid³. The thiosemicarbazones used in this reaction were prepared by the reaction of thiosemicarbazide and the corresponding aldehyde in presence of sodium acetate in water, alcohol or acetic acid as reported⁴. The thiosemicarbazones exhibit two tautomeric forms and react with 6-bromoacylbenzoxazolinones as hydrazinothiolimide form (A)⁵.

The spectral data of the compounds confirm this situation. All spectral data are in accordance with literature⁶. In ir spectra of the compounds, C=O stretching (lactam), C=C, C=N stretching and C-H bending vibrational bands exhibit expected values. The peaks at approximately 1570 and 1475 cm^{-1} are characteristic for thiazole ring (thiazole I and II bands). In uv spectrum, intensive absorption bands occur at about 340, 290, 240 and 220 nm. The peaks at 210 and 235 nm are characteristic for thiazole ring. The substituents attached to ring cause bathochromic shift. In ¹H nmr spectra, protons in structure are corresponding to chemical shift and integral values. The N-CH₃ and NH-N= group protons occur at about δ 3.35 and 5.75, respectively. Benzylidene protons (N=CH) occur at δ 7.88-8.00 in all compounds except compound 6 (δ 8.29). Hydroxyl protons are seen at δ 9.45-9.60. In mass spectrum, molecular ion peak was seen in all compounds. The base peak in compounds 1, 3, 5-8 are at m/z 295 whereas the base peak of compounds 2 and 4 are at m/z 414 and 55 respectively. In addition to molecular ion and base peak m/z 253, peaks produced by breaking of 1-2 and 3-4 bonds of thiazole ring are also seen in their spectra.

Since all compounds have one chlorine atom, $M+2$ ion peaks are seen in their spectra. The results of elemental analysis also confirm the structures of the compounds.

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